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NUTRITIONAL IMPORTANCE AND HEALTH BENEFITS OF MUSHROOM FOR WOMEN: AN OVERVIEW

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Abstract:

According to Cheskin LJ, 2008; Increasing intake of low-energy-density foods (meaning few calories given the volume of food), specifically mushrooms, in place of high-energy-density foods, like lean ground beef, can be an effective method for reducing daily energy and fat intake. Mushrooms are fungi having much nutritional value and medicinal properties and also prevent some incurable diseases like cancer. Mushrooms have long been celebrated as a source of powerful nutrients. Mushrooms are low in calories, fat-free, cholesterol-free and very low in sodium, yet they provide important nutrients, including selenium, potassium, riboflavin, niacin, vitamin D and more and having many beneficial nutrient required by women in their life stages. Some species of mushrooms are poisonous due to production of toxic secondary metabolites. But edible mushrooms are boon of God; because many researchers reported its nutritional and medicinal importance for human beings due to containing many types of vitamins, minerals and health-promoting phytochemicals. Especially women require more and different nutrition than men due to their busy and tough life style and challenging life stages. So, in this review article we are trying to summarize the importance of nutrition and health benefits of mushroom for women.

Introduction:

Since ancient times, mushrooms have been regarded as the 'food of the Gods'. The word mushroom is generally applied to edible fungi but of the many thousands of species in the world, less than half are

edible. Cultivated mushrooms are available throughout the year. Mushroom are the fleshy, spore-bearing fruiting body of fungi, typically produced above ground on soil or on its food source & describes a variety of gilled fungi, with or without stems. This term is used even more generally, to describe both the fleshy fruiting bodies of some Ascomycota and the woody or leathery fruiting bodies of some Basidiomycota. Mushrooms are a low-calorie food. Dietary mushrooms are a good source of B vitamins, such as riboflavin, niacin and pantothenic acid, and the essential minerals, selenium, copper and potassium. Fat, carbohydrate and calorie content are low, with absence of vitamin C and sodium, extensively in cooking and known as the meat of the vegetable world (Haas EM, James P., 2009).

Types of Mushroom:

Mushrooms are neither a plant nor an animal it is an odd looking group that goes by the name of fungi. It may categorize into types like button mushrooms, cup mushrooms, flat mushrooms, shiitake, oyster and brown caps etc.

Most mushrooms have been commercially grown on mushroom farms. Mostly *Agaricus bisporus*, is considered safe for most people to eat because it is grown in controlled, sterilized environments. Several varieties of *A. bisporus* are grown commercially, including whites, crimini, and portobello. Some species of mushrooms are poisonous because many mushroom species produce secondary metabolites that can be toxic, mind-altering, antibiotic, antiviral, or bioluminescent (Hall *et al.*, 2003).

of natural mushroom compounds are investigated or studied as possible treatments for diseases. Some mushroom materials, including polysaccharides, glycoproteins and proteoglycans, modulate immune system responses and inhibit tumor growth in preliminary research, whereas other isolates show potential cardiovascular, antiviral, antibacterial, antiparasitic, anti-inflammatory, and antidiabetic properties. Currently, several extracts have widespread use in Japan, Korea and China, as adjuncts to radiation treatments and chemotherapy even though clinical evidence of efficacy in humans has not been confirmed.

Mushrooms provide a powerhouse of nutrients that may help protect against some cancers. Scientists at City of Hope were some of the first to find a potential link between mushrooms and a decreased likelihood of tumor growth and development in cells and animals.

Importance of Mushroom Nutrition For Women:

There are many minerals found in mushrooms that are essential for a healthy body. The most abundant minerals in mushrooms are potassium, phosphorus, copper and selenium. There are lesser amounts of magnesium, iron and zinc.

100 gm. mushroom approximately sufficient to complete recommended Dietary Intake each day of copper, selenium, phosphorus and potassium (Nutrient Reference Values for Australia & New Zealand 2006; NUTTAB 2010) for men and women both.

Polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) is a disorder of the female endocrine system that affects an estimated 5-10% of women at reproductive age. According to research published in the *Journal of Alternative and Complementary Medicine*, Maitake mushroom extract may be a viable alternative to pharmaceutical treatment of the common female disorder polycystic ovary syndrome by encouraging ovulation.

Mushroom contains iron which is one of the keys to good health and energy levels in women. Low iron levels can be caused by a women's menstrual cycle or a problem with iron absorption. It is also a critical nutrient for a healthy pregnancy. Pregnant women require higher dietary levels of iron than their non-pregnant counterparts, according to the American Pregnancy Association. Iron is essential for the manufacture of oxygen-carrying hemoglobin of blood, and sufficient dietary iron guards against anemia and lowers your risk for premature delivery or for a low birth-weight baby. More mushrooms are especially abundant in iron and supplying half of the daily pregnancy

requirements are part of a healthy diet. Vitamin B-12, an essential nutrient found primarily in animal products, is involved in energy production and in maintaining healthy eyes, skin and red blood cells.

The mineral selenium functions as an antioxidant in the cells, guarding them from environmental damage that may cause harm to organs. Selenium also boosts immune system and helps ward off illness, especially important during pregnancy. Few plant-based foods contain much selenium, but white, portabella and crimini mushrooms supply significant amounts of this mineral to the diet. Another antioxidant, ergothioneine, helps strengthen the immune system and is also present in a variety of mushrooms, according to the Mushroom Council.

Mushroom contains copper which maintains level of R.B.Cs in the body and maintained R.B.Cs level is necessary for the women at their every stage of life especially in pregnancy stage. Mushrooms are very effective in preventing breast and prostate cancer due to presence of Beta glucans and conjugated linoleic acid having anti carcinogenic effect. because linoleic acid is helpful to suppress estrogen which is mainly responsible for breast cancer in women after menopause. the Beta glucans inhibits the growth of cancerous cells in the case of prostate cancer. In this way mushroom's nutritional value is very helpful for women's health at each and every stage of their life.

Point of Consideration About Mushrooms:

Some species of mushrooms are poisonous due to production of some toxic metabolites. There are only a small number of deadly species, several others can cause particularly severe and unpleasant symptoms. However, the carcinogens are destroyed by moderate heat when cooking (Sieger AA, 1998).

Mushroom poisoning (also known as mycetism) refers to harmful effects from ingestion of toxic substances present in a mushroom. These symptoms can vary from slight gastrointestinal discomfort to death. The toxins present are secondary metabolites produced in specific biochemical pathways in the fungal cells. Mushroom poisoning is usually the result of ingestion of wild mushrooms after misidentification of a toxic mushroom as an edible species. The most common reason for this misidentification is close resemblance in terms of colour and general morphology of the toxic mushrooms species with edible species. Even very experienced wild mushroom gatherers are upon rare occasion poisoned by eating toxic species, despite being well aware of the risks, through carelessness.

To prevent mushroom poisoning, mushroom gatherers need to be very familiar with the mushrooms they intend to collect as well as with any similar-looking toxic species. In addition, edibility of mushrooms may depend on methods of preparation for cooking. Collectors also need to be well aware that edibility or toxicity of some species varies with geographic location. More generally, and particularly with gilled mushrooms, separating edible from poisonous species requires meticulous attention to detail; there is no single trait by which all toxic mushrooms can be identified, nor one by which all edible mushrooms can be identified. Additionally, even edible mushrooms may produce allergic reactions in susceptible individuals, from a mild asthmatic response to severe anaphylactic shock (Ammirati *et al.*, 1985).

Conclusion:

Good nutrition aims to achieve and maintain a desirable body composition and high potential for physical and mental work. Women need more balanced and nutrient rich food than men due to their challenging life periods. Mushrooms are documented with anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, and immune-supporting properties. Mushrooms contain polysaccharides that are thought to inhibit tumor growth and viral infection by stimulating various cells of the immune system. Mushrooms contain proteins, carbohydrates, vitamins, trace elements, beta-glucans (sugar molecules) and naturally-occurring plant compounds like sterols, phenols, and terpenoids, which are all known to have health benefits.

Mushrooms are low in calories, fat-free, cholesterol-free and very low in sodium, yet they provide important nutrients, including selenium, potassium, riboflavin, niacin, vitamin D and more. Mushrooms contains many beneficial ingredients like water, protein, fat, carbohydrates, vitamin C, vitamin E, folate, iron, dietary fibre, niacin, riboflavin (B2) etc. Mushrooms also having medicinal properties even may help prevent against diseases like some cancer (breast cancer, prostate cancer) by modulate immune system responses and inhibit tumor growth. In this way many researchers reported that mushrooms (edible) are very healthy,

beneficial and medically approved food for human beings, documented with anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory, and immune-supporting properties. so, mushroom may fulfil many nutritional requirements of women. Therefore mushrooms have been regarded as the food of the God since ancient times.

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